

Ectoparasiticides (Insecticides/Acaricides)

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Ectoparasiticides is an antiparasitic drug used in the treatment or control of fleas, lice, ticks, mange mites, warbles and nuisance flies. They are commonly applied topically and are often lipophilic resulting in slow dermal absorption with long tissue and plasma half-lives.

The group of drugs which are used to kill the parasites that live on the body surface and their mode of action are: -

I. Organochlorines (OCS)

1. Chlorinated ethane derivatives: -

- ⇒ They include DDT (dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane), DDE (dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene), DDD (dichlorodiphenyldichloroethane) etc.
- ⇒ Mode of action – inhibit sodium conductance, result in delayed repolarization.

2. Cyclodienes: -

- ⇒ They include chlordane, aldrin, dieldrin etc.
- ⇒ Mode of action – inhibit gamma amino butyric acid (GABA), result in partial depolarization.

3. Hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH): -

- ⇒ They include benzene, hexachloride, lindane etc.
- ⇒ Mode of action - inhibit gamma amino butyric acid (GABA), result in partial depolarization.

II. Organophosphates (OPS)

- ⇒ Include coumaphos, fenthion, dichlorofenthion, trichlorophon etc.
- ⇒ Mode of action – they are cholinesterase inhibitors, result of inhibition of enzyme neurotoxic esterase.

III. Synthetic pyrethroids (SPS)

- ⇒ Include deltamethrin, permethrin, cypermethrin, flumethrin, fenvalerate etc. and is most convenient for both scabies and lice.

⇒ Mode of action – acts as neurotoxins upon sensory and motor nerves of insects causes paralysis.

IV. Carbamates

- ⇒ Primarily in poultry.
- ⇒ Include carbaryl and propoxur.
- ⇒ Mode of action – spontaneous reversible block on enzyme AchE.

V. Formamidines

- ⇒ Include amitraz.
- ⇒ Mode of action – acts at octopamine receptors sites in ectoparasites result in neuronal hyperexcitability and death.

VI. Phenylpyrazoles

- ⇒ Include fipronil.
- ⇒ Mode of action – blocks transmission of signals.

Methods of application and uses

- ❖ Pour on, spot on or spray on.
- ❖ Ear tags, collars, leg and tail bands.
- ❖ Parental treatment.
- ❖ Dusting powders.
- ❖ Aerosols.
- ❖ Baths – shampoo.
- ❖ Insecticidal collars.
- ❖ Oral preparation – cythioate (treatment of demodectic mange).

